

EUROPE BIOBANK WEEK CONGRESS 14-17 MAY 2024

POSTER SESSIONS

Abstracts

Produced by the Europe Biobank Week Programme Committee and BBMRI-ERIC's Department of Outreach, Education and Communications

Discussion and conclusion

The catalogue addresses the implementation of Open Science while increase the visibility of the service ecosystem of BBMRI-it. It will contribute to the sustainability of all biobanks. This activity has been supported by the funding of the European Union (NextGenerationEU), Italian NRRP project code IR0000031 - Strengthening BBMRI.it - CUP B53C22001820006.

Keywords

On-demand services, federated catalogue of services

P112: International Collaborative Biobanking: Shaping the Future Together

Botta-Orfila, Teresa (1); Bjelogrić, Snežana (2); Tanić, Miljana (2); Krivokuća, Ana (2); Soler-Ventura, Ada (1); González-Abuín, Noemí (1); Aragonès, Gemma (1); Djurić, Ana (2); Rodríguez-Vilarrupla, Aina (1); HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank group (1); Zoidakis, Jérôme (3,4); Fijneman, Remond (5); Castellví-Bel, Sergi (6); Cavic, Milena (2)

(1) Biobank from Hospital Clínic Barcelona (HCB) - Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (IDIBAPS) (HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank), Fundació Recerca Clínic Barcelona-Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (FRCB-IDIBAPS), Barcelona, Spain, (2) Department of Experimental Oncology, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia, (3) Department of Biotechnology, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens, Athens, Greece, (4) Department of Biology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece, (5) Department of Pathology, The Netherlands Cancer Institute, Amsterdam, Netherlands, (6) Gastroenterology Department, Fundació de Recerca Clínic Barcelona-Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (FRCB-IDIBAPS), Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Enfermedades Hepáticas y Digestivas, Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain

Introduction

Recognizing the role of cross-country collaboration in biobanking, STEPUP-IORS project (101079217) has driven biobanking initiatives through strategic partnerships, culminating in the establishment of Serbia's

rectal cancer biobank at the Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS). This pioneering effort highlights the importance of international collaboration in biobanking innovation, with efforts extending to valuable trainings enriching the global biobanking community's knowledge base.

Material and methods

In the realm of biobanking, we established a procedural framework aligned with international guidelines and regulations, comparing Spanish and Serbian contexts and prioritizing ethical-legal compliance, while enhancing human capacities at IORS through an educational program designed ad-hoc at IDIBAPS.

Results

Since 2012, the HCB-IDIBAPS biobank includes rectal cancer samples within its cohorts, through collaborations with clinical groups. With extensive experience in processing and procuring such samples to research projects, it facilitated the establishment of a Serbian rectal cancer biobank at IORS in 2023. Following rigorous one-year training, fourteen IORS researchers assumed management roles, contributing to the advancement of rectal cancer research through standardized procedures and collaborative efforts.

Conclusions

This initiative demonstrates the significant influence of the HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank in designing and implementing biobanks at partner institutions. It fosters collaboration among international centers and underscores Biobanks' pivotal role in specialized project workflows. Through meticulous collaboration, addressing scientific, legal-ethical, procedural, and human resource challenges with expert guidance from seasoned partner institutions, the first IORS cancer biobank was successfully established. This ensures optimal resources sharing and utilization for impactful research outcomes.

Keywords

cross-country collaboration; partnership; educational program

Teresa Botta-Orfila¹, Snezana Bjelogric², Miljana Tanic², Ana Krivokuca², Ada Soler-Ventura¹, Noemi González-Abuin¹, Gemma Aragonès¹, Ana Djuric², Aina Rodríguez-Vilarrupla¹, HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank group¹, Jerome Zoidakis^{3,4}, Remond Fijneman⁵, Sergi Castellví-Bel⁶, Milena Cavic²

¹Biobank from Hospital Clínic de Barcelona (HCB) - Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (IDIBAPS) (HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank), Fundació Recerca Clínic Barcelona-Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (FRCB-IDIBAPS), Barcelona, Spain. ²Department of Experimental Oncology, Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia. ³Department of Biotechnology, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens, Athens, Greece. ⁴Department of Biology, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece. ⁵Department of Pathology, The Netherlands Cancer Institute, Amsterdam, Netherlands. ⁶Gastroenterology Department, Fundació de Recerca Clínic Barcelona-Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (FRCB-IDIBAPS), Centro de Investigación Biomédica en Red de Enfermedades Hepáticas y Digestivas, Hospital Clínic de Barcelona, University of Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain.

INTRODUCTION

Recognizing the role of cross-country collaboration in biobanking, STEPUPIORS project (101079217) has driven biobanking initiatives through strategic partnerships, culminating in the establishment of Serbia's rectal cancer biobank at the Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS). This pioneering effort highlights the importance of international collaboration in biobanking innovation, with efforts extending to valuable trainings enriching the global biobanking community's knowledge base and their stakeholders (Figure 1). STEPUPIORS project has involved two biobanks: the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) Biobank and the HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank in Barcelona, Spain (Figure 1). Here we present the results at HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank.

Figure 1. Stakeholders from the STEPUPIORS project, Twinning for a European Consortium of Rectal Cancer Research Institutions Through Stepping Up Scientific, Technological and Innovation Excellence of IORS.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We established a procedural framework aligned with international guidelines and regulations, comparing Spanish and Serbian contexts and prioritizing ethical-legal compliance. A complete educational program was designed ad-hoc at IDIBAPS to train in biobanking skills IORS' staff. Figure 2 shows the timeline performed for the collaboration.

Figure 2. Timeline of the collaboration.

RESULTS

Since 2012, the HCB-IDIBAPS biobank has been including rectal cancer samples within its cohorts, through collaborations with clinical groups. This extensive experience in processing and procuring such sample types to research projects has facilitated the guidance for the establishment of a Serbian rectal cancer biobank

biobank at IORS in 2023. Following rigorous one-year training, fourteen IORS researchers assumed management roles, contributing to the advancement of rectal cancer research through standardized procedures and collaborative efforts. One of the main objectives of the STEPUPIORS project was to establish

the first Serbian biobank (Figure 3A). For this purpose, several members of the IORS team went to the HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank to receive on-site training, which was structured into eight different packages (Figure 3B) and involved several members of both teams (Figure 3C).

(A) STEPUPIORS

(B) Dissemination and outreach activities

(C)

Figure 3. (A) Objective 2 planification in the context of STEPUPIORS project (<https://www.stepupiors.eu/objectives/>). (B) Graphical representation of the 8 packages designed by HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank for the STEPUPIORS training in biobanking at FRCB-IDIBAPS in the collaboration with IORS. (C) Pictures from the training: Collaborative exchange session (left), HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank team members who participated in the training with STEPUPIORS members (middle), and all the HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank members with STEPUPIORS members (right).

CONCLUSIONS

1. This initiative demonstrates the **significant influence** of the HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank in **designing and implementing biobanks** at partner institutions.
2. It fosters **collaboration** among **international centers** and underscores **Biobanks' pivotal role** in specialized project workflows.

3. The first **IORS cancer biobank** was successfully established through meticulous **collaboration**, addressing scientific, legal-ethical, procedural, and human resources challenges with **expert guidance** from **experienced partner institutions**.
4. **STEPUPIORS** multidisciplinary project ensures optimal **resource and knowledge sharing** for **impactful research outcomes**.

CONTACT

HCB-IDIBAPS Biobank.
149-153 Rosselló street, Floor -1, 08036 Barcelona
+34 932275400 ext. 4516
biobanc@recerca.clinic.cat

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We are indebted to the patients for their generous sample donation and the nursing and clinical staff at Hospital Clínic de Barcelona for their collaboration. This study was supported by the Horizon Europe Twinning Project STEPUPIORS – 101079217 (www.stepupiors.eu).